

Precision RPS Calibration for the BICEP3 Telescope

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ABSTRACT

Here we present the results of characterization and upgrades to the Rotating Polarized Source (RPS) for the BICEP3 Telescope, an advanced refracting telescope designed to measure the polarization of the Cosmic Microwave Background at 95GHz. Characterization of the behavior of the RPS in-lab is critical for developing empirical expectations of achievable angle uncertainty when deployed in the field. Sources of error in the field include wind, adverse weather conditions, and even thermal expansion due to sun exposure of the guy wires that anchor the RPS on its mast at the South Pole. With the installation of a new high-precision encoder system enhancing position measurement accuracy and quantifying mechanical error, we present new results about the quantitative behavior of the Rotating Polarized Source and detail improved characterization and control of the RPS's behavior, towards the goal of complete repeatability and a decreased error budget from current by two orders of magnitude.

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-expanding field of cosmology, the study of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) has been pivotal in advancing our understanding of the universe's early stages. The CMB, being relic radiation from the Big Bang, is not only a window into the infancy of the cosmos but also a laboratory for testing the fundamental laws of physics. The state of the CMB's polarization carries rich information about the early universe and the physics governing it. The potential presence of gravitational waves in the very early universe would leave detectable signatures in the polarization, enabling a deeper understanding of the inflationary epoch.[1][2]

Recent theoretical developments have pointed to the possibility of parity violations in electromagnetic forces, which would upend current assumptions in the Standard Model of particle physics, opening a gateway to the discovery of new physics. Such a violation could manifest in a hypothesized phenomenon called Cosmic Birefringence, where the linear polarization of light, including that from the CMB, is rotated as it travels through space.[3] The hypothesized degree of rotation is proportional to distance traveled, rendering the CMB a premier indicator of Cosmic Birefringence. Detecting such a rotation could provide groundbreaking insights into the fundamental forces at play in the universe. However, the

measurement of this effect is challenging, given the subtlety of the signal and the immense precision required for its theoretical observation.

The BICEP3 Telescope, operating at 95GHz, is at the forefront of measurements of the polarization of the CMB. In order to constrain measurements of cosmic birefringence for the BICEP3 telescope, absolute measurements with respect to a known reference (in this case, gravity) is required, and this is the task of the Rotating Polarized Source (RPS). The characterization and improvement of the RPS is therefore fundamental to enhancing the measurement of absolute-referenced angles in BICEP3's observations. Our primary goal is to refine the RPS's capabilities to provide an absolute angle measurement with minimal uncertainty, ensuring that BICEP3 can reliably discern between genuine cosmic signals and external artifacts, necessitating a sufficiently low threshold of instrument systematic error.

The following paper is structured to provide a logical progression of our research and findings. We begin with an overview of the RPS's role in science operations, then delve into the design and functionality of the RPS, discussing the advancements made in its design and characterization. Subsequent sections are dedicated to the methodology of our benchtop characterization technique, the results obtained from the installation of a high-precision encoder, and the implications of these results for polarization angle measurement. Finally, we discuss avenues for further research.

THE ROTATING POLARIZED SOURCE

The RPS is a broadband source centered at 95 GHz that generates highly-polarized emission. At the South Pole, the RPS is installed atop a tower 200 meters away from the BICEP3 telescope. The RPS is intended to be installed and calibrated such that the orientation of the polarized emission at any time is accurately known with respect to gravity. The rotation of the system is facilitated by a ThorLabs NanoRotator NR360S precision rotation stage, capable of angular adjustments on the order of millidegrees, the desired standard for precision in absolute angle. Radiation from an internal rectangular feedhorn is highly-polarized by an 80um-pitch tungsten wire grid placed in front of it. The wire grid polarizer has a calculated total cross-polarization leakage of 0.000069%.[4] See Fig. 1 for a diagram of the system.

Fig 1: Diagram of the Rotating Polarized Source from Cornelison et al. [25, Figure 3]. An electrically chopped, quasi-thermal noise source (A) with an instantaneous 10 GHz spectrum centered at 95 GHz is fixed to an optical rotation stage (B) such that the rectangular feed horn of the source is collinear with the stage's axis of rotation. We place a wire grid (C) in front of the feedhorn to further polarize the output. We calibrate and monitor the orientation of the wire grid with respect to gravity using a high-precision tilt meter (D). [5]

In-situ, external environmental effects ranging from wind gusts to solar thermal expansion of the guy wires that anchor the RPS tower, lead to a variety of time-dependent misalignment offsets between the RPS and the BICEP3 system. In order to test and confirm expectations that certain perturbations have negligible impact on the resulting polarization measurements, the RPS was tested on an in-lab benchtop setup. This setup consists of the RPS located a known distance from a receiver consisting of a detector diode and a polarizer grid. Testing controlled perturbations in azimuth in-lab at distances of ~ 1 meter revealed unexpectedly sensitive angular dependence in polarization angle measurements, of unknown mechanism. Following more extensive investigation, the cause of the error remains undetermined. Fig. 2 displays one such perturbative test, where the RPS's azimuth angle is offset (i.e. it is pointed slightly away from the receiver). Our theoretical model predicts an error that is subdominant compared to our desired error tolerance, but we instead observed large errors that exceed our error budget, measuring in at tenths of a degree. Figure 2 shows how the azimuth offsets produce incorrect error measurements on the order of tenths of a degree. It is essential to determine the cause of this error and mitigate it, such that the accuracy of the RPS is ensured to higher tolerances; our ideal budget is order of magnitude thousandths of a degree.

Fig. 2: For these tests, the RPS was positioned at a range of offset angles in azimuth, and ten modulation curves were taken at each offset, allowing a polarization angle to be returned from receiver measurements. Plotted here is the error between the receiver-determined polarization angle, versus the RPS’s commanded polarization angle.

The data points in Fig. 2 were created in the following way: each data point represents the average result of ten independent modulation curves at a given angle, with error bars x2 plotted. A modulation curve is a set of 13 timestreams of data that is recorded at 30-degree angular separations, such that the RPS rotates around 360 degrees. See Fig. 3 below.

Fig. 3: An example modulation curve output. This modulation curve from Cornelison (2023) [5] plots the intensity output for a receiver with orthogonal pairs; in our case our in-lab receiver, the “ISAAC”, measures just one polarization axis. In order to determine the angle of polarization that the RPS is at, the phase of a sine wave is fitted to the recorded intensities.

The azimuth angle offset-dependent behavior in Fig. 2 is of high priority to demystify, as in the field there will be time-variant sources of perturbation in azimuth and other parameters, due to wind, thermal expansion, mechanical slop, etc., making it crucial to have a precise

quantitative understanding of the effects of perturbations on the receiver-measured polarization angle.

The cause of these highly repeatable perturbations is not precisely known. One valuable method for measuring and mitigating issues of this sort is to have systems that measure various perturbed parameters in real-time, such that data calibrations can be performed during post-processing. An existing case of this methodology is the high-precision tilt-meter that records measurements of the one tilt-axis of the system with respect to gravity at millidegree resolution, at a recording rate of 0.5Hz. With a careful installation procedure, the tiltmeter and RPS are rigidly installed on the same aluminum base plate, and field measurements have shown an improvement of 30% in final scatter of measured polarization angle.[5] Another critical feedback system is a system ensuring repeatable and accurate rotation of the polarization angle. This beneficial system takes the form of an absolute angle encoder, which is one of the focuses of this paper.

AUTOMATION OF AZIMUTH OFFSET TESTS

Previously, the azimuth offset tests performed as shown in Fig. 2 were done by hand with a high-precision ruler to achieve the correct offset angle. Another upgrade installed on the RPS for this project was the addition of a second ThorLabs NanoRotator stage to command and control the azimuth offsets central to these tests via computer, rather than by hand. The addition of a second rotation stage enabled complete automation of the azimuth offset tests, enabling a higher rate of data acquisition for the broader RPS project, and also improved repeatability. Fig. 4 below shows the results of an azimuth offset test as shown in Fig. 2, now with complete automation.

Fig. 4: The results of a fully-automated azimuth offset test.

As before, each individual data point represents ten modulation curves performed at a given azimuth offset angle. These automated tests were taken without the wire grid attached to the RPS due to the accidental damaging of one of the wire grids (although our receiver, the ISAAC, still possessed its wire grid), and in this test we observed that without the wire grid on the RPS present, the feedhorn displays an apparent 7-8 degree offset in polarization angle, even though it was visually aligned to zero. There was some evidence for this behavior in tests performed a year ago, which this now confirms, providing a clear result that should be examined in depth in future tests; this phenomenon should be fixed by the installation of a new feedhorn. Thus, the addition of automation has not eliminated the offset-dependent errors we have observed, but the installation of the automated rotation stage does improve repeatability and has enabled avenues for further inquiry.

THE HIGH-PRECISION ABSOLUTE ENCODER

The goal of installation of a high-precision absolute angular encoder is to independently verify in real-time the angular position of the RPS wire grid polarizer. The readheads that report the encoder's angle are carefully anchored with respect to a known reference surface: the aluminum base plate that holds the tiltmeter. Currently, the known position of the RPS's polarization angle is solely the angle that we commanded the system to slew to. By installing a high-precision encoder, we are able to verify the precision and accuracy of the system's control & performance. This allows us to account for a swath of mechanical calibration uncertainties which could be contributing to the resultant error observed in tests, such as backlash. No secondary feedback system has been in-place to verify final position angle, although many tests of positioning angle were conducted in-lab which verified a high degree of precision, but lower accuracy due to mechanical errors. The ThorLabs NanoRotator installed on the RPS is capable of generating rotation stage angular displacements of 0.00021 degrees.[5] This precision is satisfactory for a milli-degree tolerance for the absolute angular precision. Homing repeatability

for a given modulation curve has been previously achievable to 0.003 degrees thanks to the installation of a high-precision homing sensor. Unfortunately, following in-lab manual testing, backlash on the order of 0.06 degrees was discovered, which, while not expected to cause the offset-dependent error previously mentioned, is a crucial cause of error that should be mitigated. An absolute encoder allows us to quantify and calibrate against backlash, and furthermore have a consistent zero-position across power on/off and disassembly/reassembly cycles, rendering it a valuable asset for long-term repeatability.

Extensive research was performed to ascertain the best encoder system to install on the RPS. Below is a table compiling several options that were considered in the research process. An absolute encoder was selected that can yield angular measurements below 1/1000th of a degree (3.6 arc-seconds). Repeatability of measurements over large time intervals is a further concern, and so an absolute encoder that can report an angle value immediately following power-on (as opposed to relative, or integral encoders), is essential. The encoder must be robust against continuous sub-zero temperature measurements, and it furthermore must have a design that is easily integratable with the current RPS, and operable inside of the tight, weather-reinforced enclosure that the RPS is placed in at the South Pole. Furthermore, the encoder should have a high degree of mechanical tolerance against wear or scuffs, as the RPS is regularly disassembled and reassembled at Pole.

Encoder	Select ed?	Accuracy	Cost	Operating Temp	Comments
Renishaw REXA30 Optical Absolute Angle Encoder + x2 RESOLUTE ETR Readheads	Yes	+/- 1 arcsec (0.00028 deg)	\$7600	-40 to 80C	Dual-readhead summing enables high resolution and manages concentricity and ellipticity error; very durable; robust against low encoder signal; 3-week lead time.
Renishaw/RLS AkSIM-4 Magnetic Rotary Absolute Angle Encoder	No	+/-15 to +/- 36 arcsec (0.0042 - 0.01 deg)	\$1500	-40 to 105C	Not easily installed on RPS; 4-week lead time; low resolution.
Heidenhain ECA-4000 Series Absolute Optical Angular Encoders	No	+/- 1.5 to +/-3 arcsec (0.0004 to 0.0008 deg)	\$4700	0 to 40C	>10 weeks lead time; unsuitable temp. range
RCN 8001 Integral Bearing Absolute Angle Encoders	No	+/-1 to +/- 2 arcsec (0.00028 - 0.00056 deg)	\$12000	0 to 40C	>10 weeks lead time; not easily installed on RPS; unsuitable temp range.

Table 1: A selection of encoders intensively researched as candidates for installation on the RPS.

Following weeks of research, calculation and discussion, the Renishaw REXA30 Absolute Encoder Ring + 2x RESOLUTE Readheads was ordered. The Renishaw REXA30 steel ring + RESOLUTE Readhead combination offers a variety of benefits suitable for our system, and possesses a strong degree of spatial compatibility with our system for simple installation.

The operation of the encoder system is as follows: a 30um-pitch laser-ablated scale (Fig. 5) is read by two high-speed optical readheads spaced 180 degrees apart, on opposite sides of the encoder ring. By recording real-time simultaneous measurements from the two readheads and summing the two readheads' output, this process of dual linear summing enables an even higher angle measurement accuracy, and nullifies the effects of any concentricity and ellipticity of the system. The two readheads are capable of reading off the position of the system immediately following power-on, with no RPS rotation necessary. A unique bit signature encoded in the line pattern is read off by each readhead, and with two readheads installed, the system possesses an angular resolution of 0.0003 arcseconds, a sub-divisional error of 0.04 arcseconds, a total installed accuracy below +/- 1 arcsecond, and repeatability of 0.01 arcsecond.[6] This incredible resolution and performance is satisfactory for the RPS.

The encoder ring is made of 303/304 steel, and possesses an outer diameter of 200mm, and an inner diameter of 136mm. This size was selected to allow for accessible installation and removal of the ring (Fig. 6). In order to install the ring onto the rotor of the Thorlabs NanoRotator, a version of the existing aluminum connector plate with a new extended outer flange was machined. The aluminum plate continues to act as the main connector plate between the rotation stage and the polarization source; the encoder is simply bolted directly to the plate's outer flange to ensure the most direct and stable installation.

Fig. 5: Sample image of the laser-ablated scale on the REXA30 ring. Credit: Renishaw.

Fig. 6: REXA30 Ring (green) installation model for the RPS. The ring is directly bolted to an aluminum plate that holds the polarization structure (shroud and wire grid), and the RPS polarization source electronics.

Several mechanical properties of the readhead-encoder system were analyzed to ensure correct performance. The system is assembled at 20C, but will be operating in temperatures around -20C, and as low as -40C, leading to a temperature tolerance of ~60C. This necessitated thermal contraction calculations. The Renishaw readheads are to be positioned 0.8mm radially above the readhead, with an installation tolerance of +/- 0.15mm. At 200mm separation, mounted on 6061 aluminum with a CTE of 23.7 $\mu\text{m}/\text{C}/\text{m}$, the system is expected to contract by 0.28 mm, or 0.14 mm radially (Fig. 7). This is within the tolerance of the readheads, and so is not expected to be an issue. Moreover, the encoder ring itself will also shrink by a predicted radial value of 0.093mm (a calculate result of the differential contraction from having a steel ring bolted to an aluminum support structure), resulting in a relative radial change of only ~0.05mm, well within the operation tolerances of the readheads.

Fig. 7: Design for the readhead support structures. The readheads are visible, shown here in gray. This removable aluminum plate is optimized for rigidity, and spacing of the readheads conducive to continued operation in the face of thermal contraction.

A further improvement in microstepping capability has been enabled by the installation of a new Benchtop Stepper Motor Controller (BSC), from Thorlabs. This new benchtop stepper motor controller enables a positioning resolution of 2048 microsteps per mechanical step of the NanoRotator motor—a factor of x16 improvement in control resolution. For this upgrade, we worked to ensure compatibility with the existing suite of python scripts that allow interfaces between the serial motor controller and a PC; due to the increase in microsteps, the resultant constraints on acceleration, velocity, and positioning required a deep dive into the python script software employed for driving the RPS to a particular angle.

ABSOLUTE ENCODER TESTS & RESULTS

The predominant known general mechanical error prior to the installation of the encoder is rotary backlash in the ThorLabs NanoRotator. Backlash most commonly manifests after the rotation stage has been driven in one direction, when it attempts to return in the opposite direction. Causes of backlash in the RPS system include spacing imperfections between the worm gear and main gear that turns the rotor of the RPS. The encoder is targeted to manage this by reporting live measurements of absolute angular position, such that backlash will become readily and quantifiably apparent to high precision. Any other sources of mechanical slop affecting the commanded vs actual position of the RPS during operation will manifest in this system, and here we demonstrate for the first time that the system possesses a periodic backlash on the order of tenths of a degree, a crucial result identifying a new source of error in the system at a significant magnitude.

Fig. 8: Diagram labeling coordinates for encoder motion.

RPS Angle vs Encoder Measured Angle, Readhead Summation

Fig. 9: Data demonstrating an angle-dependent error in the RPS rotation stage. The data present represents ten modulation curves, with the plotted points representing the difference between commanded angle and measured encoder angle. Each encoder angle measurement is the linear summation of the two readheads’ outputs, a method that allows high precision.

Figure 9 shows the results of ten modulation curves over which data was gathered. There are a number of insights to be drawn from this data. First, there is an apparent angle-dependent error that is highly repeatable. We hypothesize that this error is enabled by mechanical slop in the system. The mechanical driver of this system is likely the radially asymmetrical mass balance of the RPS electronics. In order to examine whether this is the cause, it is necessary to have a calibration run to differentiate any rotation stage-specific angle-dependent behavior. Fig. 10 displays the result of the difference between RPS commanded angle and encoder-measured angle, with the RPS electronics, polarization wire grid, and shroud all removed. Thus, the rotation stage rotor is balanced and symmetrical about the roll axis, because the only attached mass is the encoder ring itself.

Fig. 10: RPS-Encoder differential angles without RPS electronics installed. The mechanical cause of this, which is larger than the estimated magnitude of known backlash, is not known, but attributable to systematic error of some mechanical aspect of the rotating stage.

Fig. 11: RPS-commanded angle error, as recorded by the encoder, and calibrated against modulation curves without RPS electronics attached. The erroneous angle offsets presented here are repeatable and follow a consistent pattern. Note that +180 is not displayed because this data was not included in the encoder-ring-only modulation curve test.

In order to determine how the mass of the RPS electronics + polarization shroud affects the resultant angle-dependent error, we subtracted the offsets graphed in Fig. 10 from the offsets in Fig. 9. The results of this data calibration are shown in Fig. 11, again as offsets recorded across ten modulation curve tests. This result is highly consistent with mechanical backlash. From these ten runs, the magnitude of total backlash has an average of 0.13399 degrees, with a maximum of 0.13937 degrees and a minimum of 0.12687 degrees recorded.

The single-direction backlash (of about 0.067 based on the previous average) agrees with previous estimated values of mechanical rotary backlash tested by hand-in-lab. Furthermore, there is a clear and repeatable dependency in the magnitude of error as a function of angle.

Fig. 12: Views of the RPS electronics housing; in this picture, the RPS is at 0 degrees. It is clear how the center of mass of the system is radially offset from the axis of rotation of the system. Thus, torque can be exerted on the mechanics of the rotation stage by gravity as it rotates about the roll axis.

A likely mechanistic explanation for this is that the slop inherent to the rotor-stator coupling of the NanoRotator rotation stage permits backlash to appear as the mass of the RPS electronics is rotated incrementally about the roll axis (Fig. 12). The backlash would naturally be expected to reverse in magnitude as the RPS electronics crosses the meridian, and so the torque due to gravity reverses direction.

DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

It is unlikely that the mechanical slop-induced errors discovered here are the direct cause of the azimuthal offset behavior observed in the RPS. Nevertheless, this work has revealed and quantified new systematics and erroneous behavior of the RPS that is of the order of magnitude of error that we seek to remove. We have determined that the mechanical imbalance of the RPS contributes to an error in the commanded vs actual RPS polarization angle at tenths of a degree magnitude, a discovery that represents a significant step towards a mitigation of sources of error. In order to mitigate the effects of backlash, modulation curves can now be more accurately implemented by using the angles recorded by the encoders, instead of the RPS commanded position, as shown by this diagram, to fit an angle during azimuth offset tests.

Future tests to perform include a completely automated azimuth test with angle recordings gathered by the encoder system, which will likely reveal a different distribution of azimuth-dependent error. Moreover, with more test run data, the mechanics of the ThorLabs NanoRotator can be examined with high accuracy, such as the accuracy and precision of the

stepper motor, the homing precision, and the extent of error dependency on system mass imbalance. This will be aided by a more detailed examination and testing of backlash. Suggested tests for this include continuous encoder measurement tests at constant rotation speed, and variable load tests to isolate and remove backlash. One mechanical solution to the backlash could be installation of a spring-loaded worm gear.

Secondly, it is essential to investigate the repeatability of the unusual angle-dependent behavior associated with the rotation stage itself, as determined by the modulation curve presented in Fig. 10 *sans* RPS electronics and mass imbalance. This should be investigated by disassembling the RPS electronics and running repeated tests of the rotation stage with only the encoder ring attached. Although only one run of data in this configuration was gathered, this is very likely a repeatable error. Other future test recommendations include RPS-commanded angle measurements under differing environmental conditions, such as running the test under cooled conditions to determine any temperature-dependent behavioral changes in the performance of the rotation stage and the encoder system. It will lastly be necessary to further characterize the systematics of the encoder itself, and to ensure repeatability of encoder installation under all conditions. Running heating and cooling cycles on the RPS without changing the angle of the rotation stage is a valuable way to characterize system changes due to thermal contraction and expansion.

Thus, with the successful installation of a high-accuracy and high-precision absolute encoder, new systematic errors on the order of magnitude of tenths of a degree have been discovered and quantified, presenting several future avenues of inquiry for the continued investigation of the RPS azimuth-dependent angular behavior.

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